

CONTEMPORARY CRIMINALISTIC METHODS AND TECHNIQUES

Mihajlo Sviderski

D.Sc. candidate

mihajlo_svid@hotmail.com

Marina Malish Sazdovska

Faculty of Security – Skopje

marina.msazdovska@uklo.edu.mk

ABSTRACT

Criminalistic science, as an integral part of the trichotomous science of criminalistics – alongside criminalistic tactics and methodology – constitutes a distinct field. It addresses the scientific and technical aspects of discovering, processing and interpreting material traces. In addition, it encompasses techniques for registering and identifying persons and objects. The purpose of applying these methods and techniques is to prevent crime, detect criminal acts and perpetrators, as well as provide evidence.

Beyond traditional approaches, numerous modern methods have been introduced in recent years as a result of technological development. The paper examines contemporary criminalistic methods and techniques that significantly contribute to the efficient detection and proof of criminal acts, as well as the determination of perpetrators' identities.

Keywords: Criminalistic technique, methods, techniques, etc.

INTRODUCTION

Criminalistic technique, as a separate area of criminalistics, first emerged from the need to analyze crime scenes, determine perpetrators' identity, collect material evidence and undertake other measures to fully elucidate crimes. Methods applied within criminalistic technique may derive from the natural and technical sciences, as well as from the social sciences.

Methods in criminalistic science are scientifically based ways of understanding, researching and addressing objects of criminalistic knowledge. (Малиш Саздовска, 2025, стр. 13)

Today, numerous modern methods can be applied within the field of criminalistic technique, such as the use of drones during crime scene inspections, electronic crime scene sketching, pupil dilation analysis as a preliminary examination, blood alcohol analysis without blood sampling, and others.

USE OF DRONES

Drones have recently become a valuable technical and technological tool in police work, intelligence, and even in combat operations with the formation of special squadrons.

In the Republic of North Macedonia, drones are used to detect and extinguish fires, as well as in large-scale police operations – for example. searching for criminals or

identifying individuals who set forest fires. Internationally, drones are also used for forensic purposes: in the United Kingdom for monitoring crime scenes, in France for better inspection of major traffic accidents, and for investigating and surveilling locations of mass public gatherings, etc. (Sokoloski, 2024).

According to the 2022 Annual Report of the Committee for the Investigation of Air Accidents and Serious Incidents drones have a wide range of applications, including traffic monitoring, rescue operations in difficult-to-reach areas, agricultural use and the transport of material goods. Despite their extensive potential for application, regulatory gaps remain the primary challenge. The Republic of North Macedonia is at an early stage of regulating this field and the existing vacuum hinders the full development and application of the opportunity arising from drone technology. It is evident that this area will develop rapidly, making the immediate implementation of European and international regulations essential to avoid technological and operative limitations. In line with the Committee's needs, training was provided to two external investigators in drone operation and field recording during on-site inspection of air accidents. (Annual report on Work for 2022, 2022)

Based on the Annual Report of the Committee for the Investigation of Aircraft Accidents and Serious Incidents, it can be concluded that the use of drones in investigating such accidents and incidents is of substantial importance and that measures should be taken as soon as possible to enable drone application in the country. (Annual report on Work for 2023, 2023)

As noted in the digital forensics section, the Department of Forensic Examinations also analyzes electronic evidence stored in mobile devices and drones, with the aim of identifying evidence relevant to criminal investigations.

ELECTRONIC CRIME SCENE SKETCHING

Various software solutions allow crime scene technicians to create electronic sketches of crime scenes instead of relying solely on manually sketching.

Computer-Aided Design (CAD) systems can be used in combination with Rolleimetric MR-2 camera to produce high-quality electronic crime scene sketches. The new photogrammetric system includes lightweight cameras and computer equipment for processing image data. Its application in forensic science is not new. Among the available CAD systems for photographic measurement, the Rolleimetric MR-2 offers several advantages that make it suitable for routine use in serious crime scene documentation.

The Rolleiflex 3003 camera operates like a standard camera, with the additional requirement that clearly visible reference targets (e.g. white discs or other markers) with known distances between them be present in the image. These reference measurements are recorded photographically alongside all other scene details. Photographers should be taken from multiple angles to ensure overlapping image data and optimal results – the more pictures are taken, the better! The final scaled sketch is produced through computer-based evaluation using system software and additional CAD tools, resulting in precise and clean representation of the crime scene. The system is also useful for documenting large-scale disaster scenes, including aerial mapping of objects separated by significant distances, such as aircraft crash sites. (Pfefferli, 2001)

Other software solutions, such as SmartDraw, also facilitate crime scene sketching and forensic diagram creation. Users can choose from predefined layouts for residential, commercial or outdoor scenes. These can then be customized using symbols representing weapons, gloves, bloodstains, and even bodies. (SmartDraw, n.d.)

POLILIGHT

Polilight is a modern criminalistic tool that uses a laser-based method to detect fingerprints.

The Polylight is a mobile device designed to detect and photograph papillary ridge traces using light of different wavelengths. In addition to fingerprints, the device can also detect other biological traces that fluoresce under specific conditions.

The device is mounted on a pedestal and photography is performed at a right angle while the device is connected to a computer. This allows for the necessary adjustment of light and other parameters. Polilight enables high-quality and efficient forensic examination of crime scenes and is equipped with features such as remote control, a graphic display, and a five-meter light guide.

The extended light guide and the remote control allow the forensic technicians to move freely around the crime scenewithout constantly repositioning the device. (Бјеловук, 2022, p. 302)

ALCOHOL BREATH TEST

The alcohol breath test has been accepted as evidence in Sweden since 1989 and holds the same legal value as a blood test. Evidence instruments may be fixed or mobile and are used in buses, cars, boats and helicopters.

Sweden applies two categories of penalties for drunk driving: one based on breath tests and one on blood tests. Breath alcohol concentration is measured in milligrams of alcohol per liter of exhaled air (mg/l). Blood alcohol concentration is measured in parts per mille (‰). The offence is classified into two levels: drunk driving and aggravated drunk driving. Criminal liability for drunk driving begins at 0.10 mg/l of breath alcohol or 0.2 ‰ blood alcohol. Aggravated drunk driving is defined at 0.50 mg/l breath alcohol or 1.0 ‰ blood alcohol.

In practice, this means that breath tests often result in lower thresholds for establishing criminal liability compared to blood tests.

Sampling procedure: The first step in a roadside sobriety test is for the driver to blow into a hand-held test instrument, which gives a result if the alcohol content in the exhaled air is above the permitted limit. The result is only reported as “positive” and “negative”. Screening may be carried out without prior suspicion of an offence. If the screening test is positive, the next step requires the individual to undergo a confirmatory breath test using an evidentiary instrument. The driver must provide two breath samples at intervals of 6 to 9 minutes. If a person refuses or is unable to provide a breath sample – such as individuals with asthma or severe intoxication – a blood sample is taken instead. The Evidenzer evidentiary instrument (used by Swedish police) employs infrared (IR) technology and measures ethanol content at four different IR wavelengths to differentiate it from other substances as effectively as possible. (Polisen.se, n.d.) This method is particularly useful in cases where individuals refuse to give blood sample.

HAIR DRUG TESTING

Drugs are stored in hair and can therefore be detected over much longer periods than in urine or blood. Therefore, hair analysis can provide valuable information about previous intake of substances – from weeks to months into the past time.

When a person takes drugs, they circulate the bloodstream, reaching the capillaries of the hair follicles. The substance is embedded in the growing hair shaft and as the hair grows, it forms a chronological record of substance intake. This means that hair analysis can show when a person last used drugs. On average, hair grows approximately one centimeter per month, although this can vary from person to person. In cases involving suspected overdose death, hair analysis can provide information about whether the person had periods of abstinence prior to death. In recent years, advanced hair analysis techniques have also been used as supplementary evidence in cases of involuntarily drug administration.

These analyses are performed in a forensic chemistry laboratories, which also provide specialized hair sampling kits. (RMV.se, n.d.)

CONCLUSION

Criminalistic science and criminalistic-technical examinations play a crucial role in criminal investigation procedures. These methods and techniques are essential for collecting relevant material traces that serve as high-quality evidence during judicial proceedings. Forensic methods and techniques are applied to answer the so-called “nine golden questions” of criminalistics, thereby completely clarifying criminal offences. Through these methods, cause-and-effect relationships at the crime scene are established and perpetrators are identified. At the same time, all necessary facts indicating motive, modus operandi, victims and other aspects of the crime are thoroughly examined.

By combining traditional and modern forensic-technical methods and techniques, conditions are created for a high-quality and efficient criminal investigation, ultimately contributing to the imposition of appropriate sanctioning for perpetrators by prosecutors and courts.

In the future, it is essential for the forensic-technical personnel in the Republic of North Macedonia to acquire advanced knowledge and practical skills related to applying these modern criminalistic methods and techniques. This will ensure their successful implementation in both fieldwork and laboratory examinations.

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